
BRAND EQUITY AND CUSTOMER PATRONAGE OF INDOMIE INSTANT NOODLES IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract: Building and properly managing brand equity has become essential for any business organizations. As such, branding has become one of the most dominant indicators in the global product performance. Customer-based brand equity (CBBE) is a valuable tool in brand positioning and evaluating their marketing strategies. The study investigated the relationship between brand equity dimensions and customer patronage of Indomie instant noodles in Enugu State. Specific objectives includes to: Examine the level of relationship between brand awareness and customer word of mouth of Indomie instant noodles in Enugu State, evaluate the extent relationship between brand association and customer repeat purchase of Indomie instant noodles in Enugu State, ascertain the degree of relationship between perceived brand quality and customer purchase intentions of Indomie instant noodles and assess the extent relationship between brand loyalty and customer referral of Indomie instant noodles in Enugu State. A well structured questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. Total population of the study was one thousand eight hundred and ten (384) which was statistically determined and conveniently selected from the three shopping malls in Enugu State namely; Shoprite, Roban Stores, Enugu Mall (SPAR). Pearson Correlation was used in testing the hypothesis. The Cronbach alpha test was used to determine the reliability of the questionnaire. It was found out that brand equity has significant positive relationship with customer patronage of Indomie instant noodles in Enugu State. Based on the findings the study recommended that: Indomie instant noodles should ensure that proper and clear message about brand attributes are embedded on the advertisements and publicity campaign in order to build good brand awareness and ensure effective awareness, advertising and publicity campaign should be carried out through the appropriate channels suited for their targeted audience in order to ensure that they are heard.

Keywords: Brand Equity, Customer Patronage, Brand Awareness, Brand Loyalty, Purchase Intention

INTRODUCTION

Brands have evolved from being a differentiator and a quality marker in the 18th and 19th century to a key business asset in the 20th century. From being a product + a name, it has evolved to a complex construct with multiple attributes playing different roles for the consumer, the trade and the company (Mohammad, 2018). Berthon, Leyland, Collins and Michael (2011) confirms that brands has evolved further to where it has become the focus and manifested itself on the unconscious individual and collective structures supporting it, where it has taken the life of its own and beyond the intentions of their creators and the

interpretations of its consumers. (Krishan & Hartline, 2001) believed that brand equity is significant in assisting consumers to process information, especially, when the information is overloaded (Krishan, et al, 2001).

Customer patronage is all about exchange of values which originated right from the barter system of trade where people exchanged goods for goods and services for services. With the advent of money which eliminated the barter system, came huge demand for product and services which translated into increased production capacity by already existing producers and market entry opportunity for new businesses. Thus, flooding the market with many competing products (similar products) seeking for consumers attention. This led producers to seek out means of differentiating their product offerings from others for easy customer identification (branding). This system which started as mere exchanging money for good and services has developed into strong sense of consumer choice and preferences as consumers seek to get value for money spent by maximizing utility through the purchase and consumption of need satisfying brands.

Instant noodles are categorized under the fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) sector which are mainly characterized by companies that supply low-cost products that are in constant high demand. Products that are classified under the FMCG banner include food, beverages, personal hygiene and household cleaning utensils. The term “fast-moving” stems from the fact that FMCG products usually have a short shelf life and are non-durable. The Nigerian instant noodles industry in recent years has witnessed a lot of new entrants which includes Mimeo, Honeywell(formerly O! Noodles), Golden Penny, Dangote, Chikki, Tummy Tummy and others with renewed product offerings which have tightened competition in the sector.

Harcourt (2020) in the report on ‘Battle of Noodles over market’ Honeywell Noodles has over the years fine-tuned its communication unorderd to engender brand loyalty by improving in taste, packaging and market spread. In the report, it also stated that according to the the Customer Satisfaction survey conducted by FinIntell, Honeywell Noodles has continued to emerge second to Indomie in virtually all the indices, beating other leading brands. With this competition came the need for strong brand management with which firms can improve their competitive position, maintain and attract new markets and increase overall profitability. With branding, firms seek a favorable way to differentiate their products from others and create a means of identity for their products in relation to others in the market. With strong brand building and positioning comes positive brand equity.

Brand equity describes a group of brand assets and liabilities connected with the brand and enhances or diminishes the value of the product or service based on the customers' perspectives; and this value may be evidenced through consumers' actions, thoughts and feelings (Kotler and Armstrong 2010; Adeyeri and Adedoyin, 2019). Equity in the words of Harcourt (2020) boosts the worth of firms and facilitates affirmative effects on the manner consumers identify a brand and consequently brings forth favorable consumer behavior. Moving further he said, it bequeaths firms with the prospect to carry and implement flourishing brand extensions which is a vital utility for business stability, rising revenues, and emergent success heights.

The importance of evaluating brand equity can be seen in the 2005 acquisition of Gillette Company by Procter and Gamble at the purchase price of \$57 billion which was 19 times Gillette’s earnings before interest, taxes,

and depreciation (Byrnes et al 2005). Why was the acquisition price so large? The value and perceived future earnings of the brand was also acquired in the deal (David et al 2007). Researchers have also found that brands with high brand equity receive a considerable purchase price, even when a company has declared bankruptcy (Kaikati and Kaikati 2003; David et al 2007). Converse, Bugle Boy, and Schwinn are noted examples of this, selling for \$117.5 million, \$68.6 million, and more than \$60 million respectively, suggesting that high brand equity can provide rewards even when a company is in a poor financial position (David et al 2007)

Statement of the Problem

Over the years there have been an intense level of competition among noodles in the market place as a result of continues growing need for fast foods by children and youths, due to this, there has been a high race by noodle producing company to provide a high level of satisfaction to customers which will lead to patronage. Giving satisfaction to customers is very important and the key creating customer loyalty and customer retention. Also in order to prevent customers switching to other brands and behavioural change to a particular brand.

Indomie instant noodles have come in a way of addressing the hunger of youth and children, but presently with the level of competition in the noodles market effective brand Dufil Prima Foods is one of the manufacturers of noodles and it has been in existence for years have to its credits different brands of indomie instant noodles in the Market place. These brands are meant for different segments in the market. Notwithstanding, the different brands and different markets they meant to carter for, Dufil Prima Foods (indomie instant noodles manufacturers) has been in the competitive market because of the desire by the market to have a taste of other brands.

Bijuna (2013) report that brands are at the heart of marketing and business strategy. Brands have a remarkable capability to impact the way people perceive the product and that brand can diminish or elevate a product. Therefore, the result strife competitiveness which indomie instant noodles and other brands has created has stated the need for brand equity to be developed by the manufacturers to fight that competitiveness. Because the patronage of any brand is based on their brand equity. These brand equity dimensions includes brand association, brand awareness, brand loyalty and perceived brand quality. The study is therefore focused on brand equity and customer patronage of indomie instant noodles.

Objectives of the Study

The broad of objective of the study was to determine the relationship between brand equity dimensions and customer patronage of indomie instant noodles. Specific objectives were to:

- i. examine the extent of the relationship between brand awareness and customer word of mouth.
- ii. evaluate the level of the relationship between brand association and customer repeat purchase intention.
- iii. ascertain the degree of the relationship between perceived brand quality and customer purchase intentions.
- iv. assess the level of the relationship between brand loyalty and customer referral.

REVIEW OF RELATED REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Brand/Branding

American Marketing Association (AMA), a brand has been defined as a “name, term, sign, symbol, or design, or a combination of them, intended to identify the goods and services of one seller or group of sellers and to differentiate them from those of competition.” A brand has been said to be name, symbol, design, or mark that enhances the value of a product beyond its functional purpose (Farquhar, 1989). Aaker (1992), supports this definition by saying that a brand thus signals to the customer the source of the product, and protects both the customer and the producer from competitors who would attempt to provide products that appear to be identical. As clearly seen in the cases of Indomie noodles verses Supreme noodles, where the later uses the same color and brand design of Indomie noodles.

Brand Elements

The following are the basic Branding Elements:

BrandName: this is simply the unique name given to a product. For example, coca cola, ford motors, Innoson motors, peak milk etc.

Slogans: these are memorable wordings attach to a brand to create favorable feelings amongst consumers. E.g. MTN everywhere you go, GLO grand masters of data, minimee taste the feeling, Indomie the difference is in the taste, etc.

Logo/ Symbols/Pictures: these are objects associated with a particular brand. It could also be a character like the skinny green cartoon character of 7up.

Keller (2013), identified the following criteria for choosing brand elements; Memorable (easily recognized and easily recalled), meaningful (descriptive and persuasive), likable (fun and interesting, rich visual and verbal imagery and aesthetically pleasing), transferable (within and across product categories and across geographic boundaries and cultures), adaptable (flexible and updatable), protectable (legally and competitively).

Brand Equity

Aaker (1991), defined brand equity as “a set of brand assets and liabilities linked to a brand, its name and symbol, that add to or subtract from the value provided by a product or service to a firm and/or to that firm’s customers (Farquhar, 1989; Tolba & Hassan, 2009; Adeyeri and Adedoyin 2019). Brand equity refers to the marketing effects or outcomes that accrue to a product with its brand name compared to those that would accrue if the same product did not have the brand name (Moolla 2010; Maduka et al 2020).

Dimensions of Brand Equity

From the various literatures of brand equity, the following dimensions or components were found to be more prominent; **brand Awareness :** In the words of Sara (2020), brand awareness means the buyer's ability to identify or recall a brand on a particular product category. Awareness can affect people's perceptions and attitudes, lead to brand selection, and be effective in strengthening brand loyalty. **Brand Association:** In the words of Adeyeri and Adedoyin (2019), this describes all issues linked with the brand and is comprised of mental thought processes, feelings, perceptions, images, experiences, beliefs, and attitudes.

It includes everything connected in memory with the brand (Kotler & Keller, 2011). brand association is a linkage a brand has positioned in the mind of customers’ ultimately which may be the characteristics of the product or elements at no cost of it. Brand association presages the extent to which a brand calls to mind the

attributes of a product category (Harcourt 2020). **Perceived Brand Quality:** Perceived quality is a subjective quality based solely on the consumer's perception, while objective quality is based on the product or production process (Nguyen et al, 2019).

Perceived quality is described as customer's perception of the overall superiority of a brand with respect to its intended purpose, and relative to alternative brands (Hsu, Hung & Tang 2012). **Brand Loyalty:** Brand loyalty was described as the level of commitment that customers feel towards a given brand, as represented by their continuing purchase thereof (Bové et al., 1995). It is a form of repeat purchasing behaviour based on a conscious decision to continue buying a product with a particular brand or trademark (Solomon & Stuart, 1997).

Customer Patronage

Customer patronage simply means the final act of purchasing a product. According to Wu, Yeh and Hsiao (2011), it is customer willingness to purchase a particular brand over again. It is development of a favorable attitude toward a brand, desire to place a particular brand at top most minds and commitment to the use of a particular product (Jalilvand, Samiei & Mahdavinia, 2011). Chen, Chen and Huang, (2012) opined that customer patronage is the commitment to use a particular brand. This commitment is usually triggered by the degree to which the brand meets customers want and expectation. Examples word of mouth, customer repeat purchase, customer purchase intention, customer referral and customer decision process.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

Figure 1 Conceptual framework

Source: Adapted from Aaker (1991), model.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on Equity Theory. The theory was first developed in the 1960s by J. Stacy Adams, who asserted that customer seek to maintain equity between the products and satisfaction accrued to consumption (Adams, 1963; Ikechie and Ambille 2021). Equity theory focuses on determining whether the distribution of resources is fair to both relational partners. This theory holds that value premium that a company generates from a product with a recognizable name when compared to a generic equivalent becomes the

rationale for customer satisfaction of the product value. The company creates brand equity for their products by making them memorable, easily recognizable, and superior in quality and reliability so as to enhance sales volume and market share through customer patronage.

Empirical Review

Mudanganyi (2019) investigated the influence of consumer-based brand equity on customer satisfaction and brand loyalty in mobile cellular services. A total of 240 respondents were sampled for the study. The results confirmed a significant relationship between the dimensions of brand equity and customer satisfaction; and also, between customer satisfaction and brand loyalty.

Adeyiri and Adedoyin (2019), examined brand equity and consumer patronage of soft drinks in Benin city, Nigeria. Using a sample of 240 respondents, their study found that there is a significant and positive relationship between customer patronage and the explanatory variables of brand awareness, brand association, and perceived quality. On the basis of these findings, they recommended that producers of soft drinks should create more awareness about their products through promotional advertisement.

Monaliza and Harriet (2020), examined the “impact of brand awareness on customer loyalty”. The respondents of this study were both staff and customers of Melcom. A simple random sampling was used in selecting 27 respondents for the study. The study concluded that brand awareness and customer satisfaction of products and services at Melcom not only dependent on the socio economic, the demographic or financial readiness but also publicity, public awareness, advertisement of the management and other Stakeholders towards them.

Bayero (2019) examined the effect of brand association on consumer patronage of GSM service providers in Kano Metropolis. The study utilized descriptive survey research design with both descriptive and inferential statistics used as techniques of data analysis. The finding of the study also revealed that the use of the celebrity for promotional activities by GSM operators has no effect on consumer patronage of service providers.

Chendo (2019) examined brand association and consumer patronage of malt drinks in eastern part of Nigeria. The examination used 399 usable duplicates of the poll for investigation. Cross-sectional overview technique was utilized while the information hotspot for investigation was essential. The outcome uncovered that the certification and social capacities have constructive critical impact on buyer support of malt drinks in eastern piece of Nigeria though close to home distinguishing proof capacity of brand affiliation has positive unimportant effect on purchaser support of malt drinks in Eastern piece of Nigeria.

Muhammad (2021) investigated the impact of brand association, brand image & brand loyalty on brand equity, using the business students from IoBM as sample. The study findings demonstrate that brand associations, brand loyalty and brand image have a positive effect on brand equity.

Abisola et al (2020) assessed brand association and affective loyalty in selected deposit money banks. The descriptive research design was adopted and the study population consists of customers of the five selected banks in Lagos State, Nigeria. Findings from the study indicate that successful brand association helps consumers to recognize customer preferences and differentiate brands from their rivals, with the result that customers are more likely to patronize their brands.

The study of Ikechie and Ambille (2021) investigated brand equity and customer patronage of electronic products in rivers state. it revealed that perceived price is the major instrument for customer satisfaction of electronic products' purchase in Rivers State.

Lina, Tala and Mohammad (2021), investigated the influence of brand equity on customer loyalty in starbucks Chain in Jordan. The study used a population 130 respondents and found that customer loyalty is significantly and positively affected by the overall brand equity and by each of its two studied dimensions. While effects of the overall brand equity ($R^2 = 0.710$) and brand awareness ($R^2 = 0.672$) on customer loyalty are close, effect of brand image is the lowest ($R^2 = 0.440$).

Sara (2020) examined the effect of brand experience on brand equity and brand loyalty through the mediating role of brand awareness, brand image and perceived quality; among complementary health insurance customers in Iran. The results of this study showed that brand experience has a significant effect on brand image. Brand experience has a significant effect on brand awareness.

Njelita and Anyasor (2020) investigated customer loyalty and patronage of quick service restaurant in Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design in which 399 patrons were sampled. Findings from the study revealed a significant positive relationship between price fairness, food quality, firm's personnel quality, customer trust, restaurant image, and restaurant's atmosphere and customer loyalty. Positive relationship was also found between customer loyalty and customer patronage.

Gaps in Reviewed Literature

From the above studies reviewed, one can easily notice that none was carried out in the FCMG (fast moving consumer goods) industry nor the instant noodles sector. It is important to note that different products may differ from each other as they each have unique characteristics of brand equity attributes which cannot be generalized to other products categories. Therefore, the determinants of brand equity need to be further validated in other product categories like the FCMG and instant noodles sector. Secondly, none of the previous studies as reviewed was carried out in Enugu state, of which our study bridges this gap by focusing on solely on Enugu state.

METHODOLOGY

A survey research design method was adopted for this study and questionnaire was used in the survey. A survey research is the collection of information from a sample of individuals through their responses to question. The data collected from surveys is then statistically analyzed to draw meaningful research conclusion. The researcher used this design because it was found appropriate for the analysing the data because its more convenient and cost effective to use due to the large population . Data used was used for this study was obtained from the customers of Indomie instant noodles in Enugu State. Data for this study was collected from primary source and direct interviews, using a well-structured questionnaire issued to customers found at the selected shopping malls in Enugu metropolis. The population of study consists of all the consumers of Indomie noodles in the three selected shopping malls used for the study. but sadly, their numbers were not obtainable because of large number of customers. Sample size was 384. Well-structured and validated questionnaire was used to gather data. The data collected, and descriptive statistics were presented and analyzed using tables,

frequencies and percentages. Pearson Correlation was used as inferential analysis for testing the research hypotheses and answering the research questions.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

TEST OF HYPOTHESES

Table 1 Correlation analysis

		Brand awareness	Brand association	Perceived brand quality	Brand loyalty	Customer patronage
Brand awareness	Pearson Correlation	1	.898**	.910**	.909**	.923**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	250	250	250	250	250
Brand association	Pearson Correlation	.898**	1	.867**	.911**	.892**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	250	250	250	250	250
Perceived brand quality	Pearson Correlation	.910**	.867**	1	.941**	.908**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	250	250	250	250	250
Brand loyalty	Pearson Correlation	.909**	.911**	.941**	1	.890**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	250	250	250	250	250
Customer patronage	Pearson Correlation	.923**	.892**	.908**	.890**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	250	250	250	250	250

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results from table 1 show a positive significant correlation between brand equity proxies and customer patronage. Item 1, which is brand awareness, shows a very high positive correlation with customer patronage at an r value of .923. Brand association on the other hand shows a high positive correlation with customer patronage at an r value of .892. Perceived brand quality is equally very highly correlated with customer patronage at an r value of .908. While, brand loyalty is correlated to customer patronage with an r value of .890. All the items from table 4.4 have an alpha or P value of .000 which is less than our significance level of 0.01 (2-tailed). this means that this result is statistically significant and did not occur by chance. Moving forward based on the above result, we conclude that they are significant positive relationship between brand equity (with emphasis on brand awareness, brand association, perceived brand quality and brand loyalty) and customer patronage of instant noodles in Enugu state.

Summary of Findings

After data analysis, the following findings were made;

- i. Brand awareness has significant positive relationship ($r=.923$) with customer patronage of Indomie instant noodles.
- ii. Brand association has significant positive relationship ($r=.892$) with customer patronage of Indomie instant noodles.
- iii. Perceived brand quality has significant positive relationship ($r=.908$) with customer patronage of Indomie instant noodles.
- iv. Brand loyalty have significant positive relationship ($r=.890$) with customer patronage of Indomie instant noodles.

Conclusion

From the findings, we conclude that brand equity dimensions namely; brand awareness, brand association, perceived brand quality and brand loyalty significantly influence customer patronage of Indomie instant noodles. In view of this findings, Indomie instant noodles need to proactively work on improving their product offerings.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made;

- i. Indomie instant noodles should ensure that proper and clear messages about brand attributes are embedded in their advertising and publicity campaign such as radio advertisement, hand bills, bill boards etc in order to build good brand association and ensure effective awareness.
- ii. Indomie instant noodles should try as much as possible to create a positive brand association so as to enable customers recognize and their product whenever it is mentioned, for example; “Indomie instant noodles, tasty nutritious just for you.
- iii. Proactive measures should be taken to ensure that they is no deviation in brand quality in order not to change the favorable quality perception of the brand.
- iv. Price adjustments should be made during times of economic hardship to ensure continual loyalty and prevent brand switching as most cases of brand switching are price induced.

Contribution to Knowledge

This research will be of great value to students who wants to conduct research on brand equity of any product. It will also help noodles companies and FMCG companies in general to understand and know how to appeal to their customers and gain more market share .

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